

SPACE ASTROMETRY

Experimental relativity: Bending of light rays in the gravitational fields of the Sun and Jupiter

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One of the classical tests of general relativity is the measurement of the bending of light rays in the gravitational field of the Sun. The astrometric satellite may be well suited for such measurements which are still of great importance because of the possibility to distinguish between different theories of gravitation. Also the bending in the field of Jupiter should be measurable with the satellite.

The gravitational deflection of light rays causes a shift of a star's apparent position by an angle D away from the gravitating body:

$$D = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma) 2GMc^{-2}R^{-1} \cot(\eta/2) = p \cot(\eta/2), \quad (1)$$

where M = mass of gravitating body and R , η are defined in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 O = observer, M = attracting body, D = displacement of star's position.

Fig. 2 S = Sun, Z = pole of scan, P = star, $D_{\perp}$ and $D_{\parallel}$ = components of displacement D .

γ is a parameter distinguishing between different theories: $\gamma = 0$ for Newtonian gravitation, $\gamma = 1$ for Einstein's theory of general relativity

and $\gamma = (1 + \omega)/(2 + \omega)$ for the Brans-Dicke scalar-tensor theory with $\omega =$ coupling constant.

Optical measurements of D (solar eclipses) have yielded typically $(1 + \gamma)/2 \approx 1.0 \pm 0.1$ m.e. (see the review by Klüber, *Vistas in Astronomy*, 3, 47, 1960). Radio interferometry of quasars have given more accurate determinations, e.g. $(1 + \gamma)/2 = 1.015 \pm 0.011$ m.e. (Fomalont and Sramek, *Ap. J.* 199, 749, 1975), but it will be difficult to get much further in accuracy with this method because of problems with refraction in the solar corona.

Bending in the field of the Sun

For $\gamma = 1$ we have for the Sun $p = 0''.00407$, yielding $D = 1''.75$ at the solar limb and $D = 0''.004$ 90° from the Sun. With the astrometric satellite the effect is observed at angles $\eta \approx 50^\circ - 130^\circ$ rather than $1^\circ - 10^\circ$ for optical and radio observations up to now. Thus the displacements are proportionally smaller and the differential effect is significant only over very wide fields or between the two superposed fields of the satellite.

With the scanning geometry in Fig. 2 we obtain the components of D normal to and along the scanning direction:

$$D_{\perp}(v) = p \frac{\cos \zeta}{1 - \sin \zeta \cos v}, \quad D_{\parallel}(v) = p \frac{\sin \zeta \sin v}{1 - \sin \zeta \cos v}. \quad (2), (3)$$

The two functions are shown in Fig. 3 for $\zeta = 40^\circ$.

We can make only differential measurements, however. With $g =$ half the basic angle, the differential shifts become

$$d_{\perp}(v) = D_{\perp}(v + g) - D_{\perp}(v - g), \quad d_{\parallel}(v) = D_{\parallel}(v + g) - D_{\parallel}(v - g), \quad (4), (5)$$

shown in Fig. 4 for $g = 42^\circ$. Even if the grid permits measurements perpendicular to the scanning direction, $d_{\perp}$ would be unobservable because a change of the spin axis direction would give a very similar result. Measurement of $d_{\parallel}$ on the other hand requires that the basic angle is stable to a few milliarcsec during one orbit. Because $d_{\parallel}(v)$ is always in phase with the periodically varying direction to the Sun we might get trouble measuring it if the basic angle changes periodically with v , which seems very probable. If this is the case, it will give difficulties also for

the determination of absolute parallaxes, since the parallactic displacement along the scan $p_{\parallel} = \tilde{\omega} \sin \zeta \sin \nu$ shows a very similar behaviour (Fig. 5). If the satellite is designed to measure absolute parallaxes, it can also measure the gravitational bending of light.

Bending in the field of Jupiter

For $\gamma = 1$ we have at mean quadrature $p = 7.61 \cdot 10^{-7}$ arcsec and $D = 0''.0082$ at the limb of Jupiter ($\eta = 19''.3$). However, we cannot measure closer than perhaps $10''$ from the limb, and it seldom happens that a star passes that near Jupiter at the right moment. The rms value of D in an annulus with radii η_1 and η_2 is $\approx p(\eta_2^2 - \eta_1^2)^{-1/2} [8 \ln(\eta_2/\eta_1)]^{1/2} \approx 0''.00027$ for $\eta_1 = 29''.3$ and $\eta_2 = 1^\circ$, within which there should almost certainly be a sufficiently bright star. Thus the effect might be statistically detectable. For the Galilean satellites, which are mostly within about 0.1° from the planet, $D_{\text{rms}} = 0''.002$, but here we must also determine their orbits etc, and their finite diameters become disturbing.

Bending in the field of the Earth

From (1) we obtain $p = 0''.00026$ for a 550 km orbit. In this case $\eta = 180^\circ - g$, yielding $D = 0''.00010$. This, however, will be indistinguishable from a change of the basic angle by twice this angle.

Whether these relativistic effects can be measured or not, it is mandatory to include them in the computation of apparent positions of the objects. A discussion of their influence on groundbased astrometry is found in Brandt, Soviet Astronomy 18, 649 and Mikhailov, Soviet Astronomy 20, 248, 1976.

Fig. 3 Absolute displacements along and normal to the scan, $\zeta = 40^\circ$.

Fig. 4 Differential displacements along and normal to the scan, $\zeta = 40^\circ$, basic angle $2g = 84^\circ$.

Fig. 5 (left) Absolute parallactic displacements along and normal to the scan. $\zeta = 40^\circ$. $p_{\perp} = -\tilde{w} \cos \zeta$.